

SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL DETERMINANTS CONDITIONING THE FEELING OF LONELINESS AMONG STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the socio-psychological determinants influencing the formation of the feeling of loneliness among students from both theoretical and practical perspectives. The purpose of the research is to conduct an empirical analysis of socio-psychological determinants that shape the feeling of loneliness among students, to identify the interrelations between these factors, and to assess the degree of their influence. The article analyzes the results of an empirical study conducted on the basis of the author's questionnaire titled "Identification of Socio-Psychological Determinants of the Feeling of Loneliness". The findings of the study reveal the key determinants associated with the experience of loneliness among students.

Introduction

In the modern era of globalization and digital communication, the forms and quality of social interaction between individuals are undergoing significant transformation. Although technological progress has expanded opportunities for communication, paradoxically it has also intensified processes of internal social isolation, feelings of loneliness, and emotional alienation. Young people, particularly students of higher education institutions, represent one of the most sensitive groups affected by this phenomenon.

The period of student life is a crucial stage for the formation of personal identity, the determination of one's social position, and the development of emotional stability. The socio-psychological experiences occurring during this period directly influence an individual's future social adaptation [4].

In psychological science, the feeling of loneliness is interpreted as a complex emotional state arising from a discrepancy between an individual's social needs and their actual social experiences [2]. This condition is determined not only by individual psychological factors but also by social determinants such as the level of social activity, the quality of friendships, family environment, communication competence, and the degree of social support. From this perspective, studying the factors that lead to loneliness is of great theoretical and practical importance for ensuring students' psychological well-being and for developing strategies of social support.

Modern studies indicate that the quality of an individual's social relationships and the level of emotional satisfaction are directly determined by socio-psychological determinants [6]. During the student years, factors such as social adaptation, communicative competence, the quality of family and group relationships, self-esteem, empathy, and social support play a particularly significant role. Through the systematic analysis of these factors, it becomes possible to identify the mechanisms underlying the formation of loneliness among students.

The relevance of this research lies in the fact that, despite the increasing social activity of young people in modern society, internal emotional loneliness, social isolation, and decreasing interpersonal trust are becoming increasingly widespread, which in turn affects the psychological stability of society [7]. Therefore, the scientific analysis of socio-psychological determinants of loneliness among students is an important and actual research issue in contemporary psychology.

Theoretical and Methodological Analysis

In modern psychology, the feeling of loneliness is interpreted as one of the most complex, multidimensional emotional states determined by numerous factors. It is characterized as a subjective experience resulting from a discrepancy between a person's social needs and their real social interactions. Theoretically, this issue is explained differently by various psychological approaches including psychoanalytic, humanistic, cognitive, and socio-psychological perspectives.

Sigmund Freud viewed loneliness as a consequence of internal conflicts within the personality. According to him, contradictions between the Ego and the Id intensify the feeling of social alienation. Alfred Adler, in contrast, associated loneliness with insufficient development of social interest. When an individual fails to perceive themselves as an integral part of society, feelings of loneliness and alienation emerge [3].

In John Bowlby's attachment theory, the roots of loneliness are connected to the quality of emotional relationships between children and their parents during early childhood. If a child does not experience sufficient affection and a sense of security at an early age, they may later demonstrate instability in social relationships and a tendency toward emotional isolation. Thus, loneliness can be viewed as a consequence of disrupted attachment patterns [7].

Erich Fromm explained inner loneliness through the social structure of modern society. According to him, technological development may unite people physically but separate them spiritually [5]. A person must discover their essence not only through social roles but also through understanding their inner self. Carl Rogers associated loneliness with the discrepancy between the ideal self and the real self: when individuals feel that they are not fully accepted by others, they tend to isolate themselves [7].

Cognitive psychologists Aaron Beck and Albert Ellis considered loneliness to be the result of distorted cognitive schemas related to oneself, others, and social relationships [3]. Irrational beliefs such as "no one understands me" or "I am not worthy of communication" lead individuals to social withdrawal. Therefore, cognitive restructuring plays an important role in reducing feelings of loneliness.

According to the theory of social needs developed by Peplau and Perlman, loneliness arises when the quantity and quality of an individual's existing social relationships do not

correspond to the level they expect [2]. As a person's social support network decreases, emotional isolation intensifies. Factors such as social acceptance, mutual trust, empathy, and communicative competence are also considered key determinants of loneliness.

The student period represents a social group in which these processes become particularly intensified. Students entering higher education institutions must adapt to a new social environment, establish friendships, and make independent decisions, which often leads to emotional pressure. Socio-psychological studies show that students with lower levels of adaptation, low self-esteem, and insufficient communicative skills experience higher levels of loneliness [7].

Additionally, weak emotional closeness with family members, lack of trustworthy communication with friends, and excessive dependence on digital communication may further intensify this condition.

Researchers such as Weiss, Heinrich, Gullone, and Russell identify several determinants influencing the formation of loneliness [1, 6]:

- Level of social support (emotional and instrumental assistance)
- Communicative competence and openness in communication
- Self-esteem and personal value system
- Sense of group belonging and social identity
- Empathy and the ability for mutual understanding
- Family environment and supportive relationships
- The replacement of real communication by virtual communication

Thus, the feeling of loneliness among students is associated with multi-level determinants, each of which directly influences an individual's social activity, self-awareness, and emotional stability. Therefore, systematic analysis of these factors, identification of their interaction mechanisms, and development of preventive psychological approaches represent an important scientific task.

Conclusion

From our conducted research, we have drawn the following conclusions:

Firstly, students' attitudes toward the feeling of loneliness depend on their social experiences at different stages of education. Third-year students, unlike first-year students, did not perceive loneliness negatively; instead, they recognized its positive aspects, acknowledging that one can realize new personal opportunities in solitude.

Secondly, first-year students tended to view loneliness negatively, citing factors such as difficulties in forming a communicative environment, challenges in adapting to new settings, and underdeveloped skills in selecting suitable conversation partners. Their negative perception of loneliness and the association of solitude with unpleasant and painful experiences prevented them from experiencing positive emotions related to loneliness and from discovering its potential benefits.

Thirdly, the social-psychological determinants of loneliness are ranked according to both personal factors (stress, frustration, shyness) and social-situational factors (ostracism, social isolation, weakened communication). Under the influence of these determinants, a student may either direct their loneliness productively, using it as a resource, or become trapped in its negative effects.

Fourthly, students' belief that all personal experiences—whether positive or negative—contribute to their development through acquired knowledge, their perception of life as a means of gaining experience, their willingness to act under risk when success is not guaranteed, and their understanding that seeking comfort and safety alone may impoverish personal growth, as well as their orientation toward learning through active engagement and subsequent application, all facilitate the recognition of the positive aspects of loneliness.

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